

DIFFERENCES IN POSTURAL STATUS BETWEEN SCHOOL ADGED ATHLETES AND NON-ATHLETES

RAZLIKE U POSTURALNOM STATUSU IZMEĐU SPORTISTA I NESPORTISTA ŠKOLSKOG UZRASTA

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SUMMARY

Background: Nowadays sport and recreational activities are kept to a minimum, which leads to a decline in physical fitness and muscular balance.

Aim: Assess the postural status of athletes and non-athletes, and establish the differences in postural status between groups.

Methods: The study included 80 schoolchildren of both sexes. Children were divided into two groups athletes from volleyball club "Futog", a primary school students "Miroslav Antić" from Futog. Physical examination evaluated the posture of the body and the existence of deformities of the skeletal system.

Results: In analyzed study groups, the higher percentage of proper body posture has been observed in the group of athletes (77.5%) compared to the group of non-athletes (67.5%). Comparing the distribution of chest wall deformities, it has been observed that in the athlete group there were no deformities, whereas in the non-athlete group pectus carinatum was present (12.5%). In both study groups, the occurrence of pelvic area deformities has not been noted. Through analysis of the values of lower limb deformity distribution, it has been observed that leg deformities were in 70% of athletes and 60% of non-athletes, while bow legs and knock knees were more common in non-athlete group. Normal arch of the foot is more frequent in the athlete group (55%) compared to the non-athlete (20%). The statistically significant difference has been noted between non-athletes and athletes regarding flat feet ($p < 0.05$).

Conclusion: General postural state is better in athletes than in non-athletes.

Keywords: postural status, skeletal deformities, volleyball players

SAŽETAK

Uvod: U današnje vreme aktivno i rekreativno bavljenje sportom svode se na minimum, što dovodi do opadanja fizičke kondicije i mišićne ravnoteže.

Cilj rada: Procena posturalnog statusa i deformiteta skeletnog sistema kod sportista i nesportista, i utvrđivanje razlika u posmatranim parametrima između grupa.

Materijal i metode: Istraživanjem je obuhvaćeno 80 dece oba pola školskog uzrasta. Ispitanici su bili podeljeni u dve grupe: sportisti Odbojkaškog kluba „Futog“ i učenici osnovne škole „Miroslav Antić“ iz Futoga. Fizikalnim pregledom ocenjivala se postura tela i postojanje deformiteta skeletnog sistema.

Rezultati: Uočena je veća procentualna zastupljenost pravilne posture tela u grupi sportista (77.5%) u odnosu na nesportiste (67.5%). Grudni koš kod sportista je bez deformiteta, dok je kod nesportista zastupljen pectus carinatum (12.5%). U obe grupe, nije uočeno postojanje deformiteta karličnog pojasa. Deformiteti nogu su prisutni u 70% sportista i 60% nesportista, dok su "X" i "O" noge zastupljenije u grupi nesportista. Normalan svod stopala daleko je zastupljeniji kod sportista (55%) u poređenju sa nesportistima (20%). U pogledu ravnih tabana uočena je statistički značajna razlika kod nesportista u odnosu na sportiste ($p < 0,05$).

Zaključak: Kompletan stanje posture je bolje kod sportista nego kod nesportista.

Ključne reči: posturalni status, deformiteti skeletnog sistema, odbojkaši

INTRODUCTION

In recent times, the human race has been affected by the positive and the negative impacts of the specific lifestyle caused by modern civilization. Doing sports, actively and recreationally, has been minimized, which consequently has led to the decline of physical fitness and the disturbance of muscle balance [1,2]. An adequate physical activity is a way of prevention of numerable health issues and possible postural disorders [3].

As a leading cause of posture deformities during the childhood there is a muscle weakness oriented to spinal, thoracic and abdominal muscles. Presently the major contributing factors are heavy school bags that they carry daily, as well as the improper sitting at school desks [4-6].

To achieve positive effects of the physical and sports activities, it is necessary to know the factors that determine their impacts on the human body, as well as how these factors are harmoniously interconnected [1]. Characteristics of the exercises and activities, characteristics of those who practice them and the environmental conditions are all important factors that every expert who trains children and youngsters has to know well and apply appropriately. This is important because of the possibility of postural disturbances in many sports disciplines, due to the asymmetrical muscular development [1,7]. Influence of sports activities on the postural status has been evaluated in many research and the conclusion remain the same, there are some positive and some negative aspects depending on sports discipline [8-10]. Positive aspects of sports are reflected in the strengthening and proper development of the musculoskeletal system in children. However, excessive of unilateral load as well as weakness of certain muscle groups can cause various defects of body posture. Even in the competitive sports, despite the fact that the trainings are guided by professional staff in proper way, there is a increased incidence of postural deformities and injuries due to

excessive overload on spinal column as well on complete body musculature [11-13]. The distinct posture that forms during sports activities due to the frequent identical movements creates torsion and shear forces. These lead to tissue and bone load, which can later cause degenerative changes [14,15].

The most frequent disorders regarding body posture in human population are: spine deformities, chest wall deformities, pelvic deformities, and lower limb deformities (legs and feet) [5,6,16].

AIM

The aim of the study is to assess the postural status of athletes (volleyball players) and non-athletes, and to establish the differences in postural status between these two study groups. We hypothesise that athletes will have less postural deformities compared to non-athletes.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

The study included 80 school children from age 11-14, both male and female. The participants were divided in to two groups. The first group (male 20, female 20) volleyball players. The second group comprised of non-athletes (male 20, female 20), pupils of elementary school "Miroslav Antic" in Futog. The criterion for entering the study was that children from birth did not have problems with the locomotor apparatus, individual diseases (rachitis, tumors, inflammations), as well as the performed surgical procedure (radiotherapy). Conducting this survey has been approved by the Local Ethics Committee. The participants and their parents have been informed about the procedure and the aim of the study, what is expected of them, as well as the confidentiality of personal information. The parents gave their signed consent for their children's participation in the study.

Examination of the participants has been conducted in the Sports Hall "Futog" in two separate appointments, due to the large number

of children. The participants have been wearing sports shorts or underwear, standing upright with feet a little apart. Physical examination has been used to assess body posture, and the occurrence of the deformities of the spine, chest wall, pelvic area and lower extremities (legs and feet).

Body posture has been inspected from the distance of 2 - 3 meters, in order to get an overview of the body constitution and body part proportion. Examination of the spine has been performed by inspecting the participants from the back and from the side, including while the child was bending over to reach the toes and the spine was coming to the fore. The occurrence of the spinal deformities was also assessed: scoliosis, lordosis and kyphosis. By examining the chest, the shape and the muscular development have been assessed, as well as deformity occurrence (pectus carinatum and pectus excavatum). The pelvic area has been inspected while standing beside the child and analyzing the position of the femur on both sides. The occurrence of lower limb deformities has also been observed (bow legs and knock knees). Fallen arches have been determined by taking a footprint (plantogram), which were then used to calculate the fallen arch coefficient with the Chessen method. Under improper posture we considered: disrupted body statics, asymmetrical posture, improper walking, along with generally bad motor skills and motor coordination.

The obtained data were analyzed using the statistical data processing program JASP 0.8.0.1. A Student's T-test was used to compare between groups. For the existence of statistically significant differences we used values $p < 0.05$.

RESULTS

Figure 1. shows percentage of the good and the bad posture, as well as the values that show the distribution of the spinal deformities in both study groups. In the analyzed study groups, the higher percentage of proper body posture was observed in the group of athletes (77.5%) compared to the group of non-athletes (67.5%) and there were statistically significant differences ($p < 0.05$). The higher percentage of spinal deformities has been noted in the athlete group compared to the non-athlete group. Lordosis and kyphosis have been observed exclusively in non-athlete group. Scoliosis was present in both athlete (12.5%) and non-athlete group (25%).

Figure 2. represents the percentage of chest wall deformities in both study groups. Comparing the distribution of chest wall deformities, it was observed that in the athlete group there were no deformities, whereas in the non-athlete group pectus carinatum was present (12.5%). In both of the groups the occurrence of pectus excavatum has not been noted.

Figure 3. shows the percentage of the pelvic deformities in both study groups. In both study groups, the occurrence of pelvic area deformities was not noted.

Figure 4. depicts the percentage of lower limb (legs and feet) deformities in both study groups. Through analysis of the values of lower limb deformity distribution, it has been observed that leg deformities were absent in 70% of athletes and 60% of non-athletes, while bow legs and knock knees were more common in non-athlete group. Normal arch of the foot is more frequent in the athlete group (55%) compared to the non-athlete group (20%). The significant difference was shown between non-athletes (45%) and athletes (7.5%) regarding flat feet ($p < 0.05$).

Figure 1. Representation of postural attitude of the body and spinal deformities

Figure 2. Percentage of deformities of the rib cage

Figure 3. Percentage of deformities of the pelvic belt

Figure 4. Percentage of deformities of the lower extremities (legs and feet) p<0.05

DISCUSSION

Deviations on the topic of postural status in school children has been a global and ever-present problem in all countries of the world. Improper body posture causes spinal deformities, which consequently interfere with normal internal organ functioning [17]. According to literature obesity, underweight, physical inactivity, and early direction to specific sport are the most important causes of the improper posture in pupils [18,19].

In our research, higher percentage of spinal deformities has been noted in the non-athlete group compared to the athlete group. Madic has evaluated the effects of carrying schoolbag on postural status of the children, and reported that children who carry their bags in one hand have deformities (pectus carinatum and scoliosis, in 84-87%)[20]. Results of our research shows that lordosis and kyphosis have been observed exclusively in non-athlete group. In a research conducted by Protic-Gava B and associates, the percentage of affected children that are not involved in sports activity is higher in percentages when it comes to lordosis (41%) compared to our results (12.5%) [21]. Regarding the presense of kyphosis (7.5%), our results are in line with the allegations in the literature. The

research conducted by Simov SB and associates in children 6-7 years of age shows the presence of kyphosis in 6.82% of respondents, whereas in the work of Djokic Z and associates in children aged 9-12 years there are almost the same representation observed as in our work 7.6% [22,23]. Scoliosis was present in both groups in athlete group (12.5%) and non-athlete group (25%). In terms of the presence of scoliosis in non-adolescent children, our results are in accordance with the previously implemented [23,24]. Pectus carinatum was present (12.5%) in the non-athlete group, while the presence of pectus exavatum was not observed in any group. Existence of pectus exavatum was not observed in the earlier conducted research by Djokic Z [23].

When it comes to deformities of the lower extremities, in Sabo E research, it is stated that the shape of legs without defects was present in 66.1% of subjects [25]. Balac has evaluated arches of the foot in swimmers and came to a conclusion that the arches of the foot are less frequently fallen compared to non-athletes [26]. Based on plantograms, the feet deformity distribution in both groups has been assessed. Normal arch of the foot is more frequent in the athlete group (55%) compared to the non-athlete group (20%). The statistically

significant difference has been noted between non-athletes (45%) and athletes (7.5%) regarding flat feet.

CONCLUSIONS

Based on the study results, the following can be concluded:

Statistically significant differences between group of athletes and non-athletes are reported in terms of proper body posture and arches of the foot.

The obtained results regarding postural status show that scoliotic bad posture is present in both children who actively play sports and those who only participate in physical education classes.

General postural state is better in athletes than in non-athletes.

Physical activity needs to be planned according to gender, age, body composition and placed in correlation with current physical and functional state of the individual.

REFERENCES

- Balashova ER, Pleshchinskii IN, Ereemeev AM. Motor and autonomic asymmetries in athletes with different specializations. *Human Physiology* 2004;30(5):591-5.
- Milenkovic S, Kocijancic R, Belojevic G. Left handedness and spine deformities in early adolescence. *Eur J Epidemiol* 2004;19(10):969-72.
- Grivas TB, Arvaniti A, Maziotou C, Manesioti MM, Fergadi A. Comparison of body weight and height between normal and scoliotic children. *Stud Health Technol Inform* 2002;91:47-53.
- Grivas TB, Vasiliadis ES, Polyzois VD, Mouzakis V. Trunk asymmetry and handedness in 8245 school children. *Pediatr Rehabil* 2006;9(3):259-66.
- Lafond D, Descarreaux M, Normand MC, Harrison DE. Postural development in school children: a cross-sectional study. *Chiropractic & Osteopathy* 2007;15(1):1.
- Milenkovic S. Determining differences in postural, anthropometric and kinesics area at the beginning and the end of a school year. *FU Phys Ed Spor* 2000;1(7):39-48.
- Yoo JC, Suh SW, Jung BJ, Hur CY, Chae IJ et al. Asymmetric exercise and scoliosis: A study of volleyball athletes. *J Korean Orthop Assoc* 2001;36(5):455-60.
- Grabara, M. Analysis of body posture between young football players and their untrained peers. *Human Movement* 2012;13(2):120-126.
- Becker TJ. Scoliosis in swimmers. *Clin Sports Med* 1986; 5(1):149-58.
- Śławińska, T. Rożek, K. Ignasiak, Z. (2006). Body asymmetry within trunk at children of early sports specialization. *Polish J Sport Med* 2006;22(6):97-100.
- Bubanj S, Milenković S, Stanković R, Bubanj R, Živković M, Atanasković A, Gašić T. The correlation between explosive strength and sagittal postural status. *Facta universitatis-series: Physical Education and Sport* 2010;8(2):173-81.
- Malzac A, Barros Filho TE. Morphometry of the spinal canal at cervical region in asymptomatic military young men. *Acta Ortop Bras* 2002 Dec;10(4):40-51.
- Meyer C, Haumont T, Gauchard GC, Leheup B, Lascombes P, Perrin PP. The practice of physical and sporting activity in teenagers with idiopathic scoliosis is related to the curve type. *Scand J Med Sci Sports* 2008;18(6):751-5.
- Ribeiro CZ, Akashi PM, Sacco ID, Pedrinelli A. Relationship between postural changes and injuries of the locomotor system in indoor soccer athletes. *Rev Bras Med Esporte* 2003;9(2):98-103.
- Tanchev PI, Dzherov AD, Parushev AD, Dikov DM, Todorov MB. Scoliosis in rhythmic gymnasts. *Spine* 2000;25(11):1367-72.
- Zivkovic D, Milenkovic S, Drobnjak D. Stanje posturalnih poremećaja i telesnih deformiteta dece mlađeg školskog uzrasta u opštinama Zaječar, Kruševac i Čačak. *Sport Mont*, 2 2004;3(2):421-6.
- Korovessis P, Koureas G, Papazisis Z. Correlation between backpack weight and way of carrying, sagittal and frontal spinal curvatures, athletic activity, and dorsal and low back pain in

- schoolchildren and adolescents. *J Spinal Disord Tech* 2004;17(1):33-40.
18. Ostojic Z, Kristo T, Ostojic L, Petrovic P, Vasilj I, Santic Z. Prevalence of scoliosis in school-children from Mostar, Bosnia and Herzegovina. *Coll Antropol* 2006;30(1):59-64.
19. Maksimovic, N. Milosevic Z. *Stil zivota mladih Vojvodine*. Novi Sad: Fakultet sporta i fizickog vaspitanja i Savez za skolski sport i olimpijsko vaspitanje grada Novog Sada, 2008.
20. Madic D. Relacije motoričkog i posturalnog statusa dece predškolskog uzrasta u Vojvodini. "Proceedings of"Anthropological status and physical activity of children and youth. 2006;40:185-91.
21. Protić-Gava B, Šćepanović T, Batez M. Body posture in young schoolchildren in a Novi Sad elementary school. *Reasrch in Kinesiology* 2013;41(2):146-9.
22. Simov SB, Minić SM, Stojanović DO. Učestalost pojave lošeg držanja tela i ravnih stopala kod dece predškolskog uzrasta. *Apollinem medicum et aesculapium* 2011;9(2):5-8.
23. Đokić Z, Stojanović M. Morfološke karakteristike i posturalni status dece od 9 do 12 godina na području Sremske Mitrovice. *Opšta medicina* 2010;16(1-2):41-9.
24. Ilić D, Đurić S. Postural status model younger school age children. *Activities in physical education and sport* 2014;4(2):120-4.
25. Sabo E. Postural state of preschool children on territory of Vojvodina. *Fizička kultura* 2006;60(2):157-64.
26. Balac M. Stanje svodova stopala kod plivača SAP Vojvodina, Fakultet fizičke kulture, Novi Sad, 1984.

KONFLIKT INTERESA

Autori izjavljuju da prilikom sprovođenja ovog istraživanja i obrade rezultata nisu imali nikakav konflikt interesa.

COMPETING INTERESTS

The authors declare that they have no competing interests.

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PREDATO U ŠTAMPU: 19.04.2017.

PRIHVAĆENO ZA ŠTAMPU: 25.11.2017.